

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGINEERING AND COMPUTER GRAPHICS TRAINING

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the use of information technology in the process of teaching students. Methods are presented to improve the level of education and quality of young specialists from technical universities and the use of computer program systems in the implementation of drawings and projects.

Keywords: information technology, educational process, computer graphics, adaptation, descriptive geometry, method.

Improving the technology of traditional methods of teaching graphic training to students of technical specialties is the use of information technology in organizing the educational process, i.e. the use of computer graphics and innovative technology in the process of teaching engineering and computer graphics. The disciplines that form the initial skills of graphic engineering include descriptive geometry, engineering and computer graphics. The process of studying descriptive geometry coincides with the period of adaptation of students in a higher educational institution. In the process of studying engineering graphics and descriptive geometry, the automation of drawing and graphic work acquires special importance, when at a certain stage of the educational process the acquisition of new graphic skills inherent in computer graphics is required.

Problem statement and research method. In this regard, the main objectives of the Department of “Descriptive Geometry, Engineering and Computer Graphics” of TSTU are the following:

1. To improve the process of teaching students of technical areas and specialties in engineering and computer graphics in the conditions of global informatization and computerization of professional activities and graphic training of future specialists;
2. To facilitate the understanding and mastery by younger students of a labor-intensive course in engineering and computer graphics in the context of a shortage of study time allocated by the State General Education Standard for the study of this fundamental general engineering discipline;
3. To increase the efficiency and quality of general engineering graphic training for students of technical specialties, contributing to the formation of the engineering competence of future specialists and the compliance of TSTU graduates with the increased qualification requirements imposed on them by the information technology society [1].

The main task of the department at this stage is to create an educational and methodological complex that would allow teachers to more effectively organize the educational process and conduct knowledge control in the disciplines studied at the department. Research results and discussion. The development and testing of teaching materials is a long and labor-intensive process and includes the following types of work to create didactic units:

- adjustment of work programs in the disciplines being studied, where emphasis should be placed on the use of computer graphics tools in the learning process and when performing graphic work;

- creation of educational and methodological developments and teaching aids to facilitate students' perception of the disciplines they study, containing the necessary material for students' independent work, during which the foundations are laid for the creative and cultural self-development of future specialists;

- creation and improvement of demonstration and poster materials that will help organize classroom work with students and help increase the efficiency and visibility of the educational process;

- development of test tasks in descriptive geometry and engineering graphics for intermediate and final control and assessment of knowledge in the disciplines studied.

In order to increase the intensity of studying the disciplines "Descriptive Geometry" and "Engineering and Computer Graphics" in the process of teaching students, it is planned to use electronic methodological developments that can increase the efficiency of the learning process. Numerous attempts to adapt AutoCAD to the needs of domestic designers have led to the emergence of many inexpensive two-dimensional CAD graphic editors. It is in this category that the Russian programs Kompas, AutoCad, Solidwords. The analysis showed that the most convenient for use in teaching the basics of computer graphics is CAD KOMPAS, intended for direct design in mechanical engineering [2]. The Kompas system fully ensures the creation of a complete computerized training course "Engineering Graphics", as well as the use of software for performing graphic work provided for in the work program for this discipline. The introduction of computer graphics into the educational process naturally does not replace traditional engineering graphics classes, in which the student gains initial drawing skills. The use of computer graphics allows us to solve at the modern level such educational tasks as labor polytechnic and vocational training of students of technical specialties for the conditions of modern production; formation of the foundations of computer engineering graphics; ability to prepare drawing and graphic documentation using CAD design.

In the current conditions, the basic software tool can be considered the “KOMPAS-K3” geometric modeling system, which is designed to create and display models of three-dimensional objects in the process of performing design, engineering and engineering work. You can perform Boolean union, intersection, and subtraction operations on object models, which also result in 3D solid models.

The K3 system makes it possible to perform the following types of work: designing and editing the external shape of products; obtaining and viewing realistic halftone images of designed objects; solving layout problems. The creation of a three-dimensional model of an object is carried out in stages. First, a blank of the designed object is created. Elementary bodies (parallelepiped, cylinder, cone, truncated cone, sphere, torus), bodies of rotation, extrusion bodies (prisms) can be selected as blanks. In the section “Projection method and graphic methods for constructing an image,” almost all tasks can be performed in the “KOMPAS-K3” system. The section “Sections and sections” is perfectly illustrated with sections (cuts) in a rectangular isometric projection. The included assembly unit drawing files can be used when studying the “Assembly Drawings” section, in particular for detonation. Experience has shown that the use of modern software in engineering and computer graphics classes activates the cognitive activity of students, leads to the development of spatial concepts, imaginative thinking based on the analysis of the shape of objects. It is also extremely important that the use of CAD eliminate unproductive elements of students’ graphic activity [3].

Conclusion. It should be noted that the use of computer technology in engineering education has become a socio-economic need, and engineering graphic education, implemented without the use of information technology, cannot be considered modern.

LITERATURE

1. Troshin V.V. Computer in a drawing lesson // School and production, 1991, No. 7. - P. 55-58.
2. Kheifets A.L., Engineering computer graphics. AutoCad and Compass. Teaching experience and open-mindedness. M.: Dialog-MEPhI 2004 -432p.
3. Azimov T.D., Baltabaev K.K., Azimov A.T. On some issues regarding the innovative activities of teaching staff of the Uzb R. Toshkent 2019.